

Cyber Security Laws & Policy: A Case Study

Jayshiv Limbasia

Department of Computer Science and Cyber Security, University of Newhaven

ABSTRACT

In the modern digital age, the widespread use of e-commerce and communication technologies brings both advantages and drawbacks, akin to a double-sided coin. Cyber-crime encompasses illicit activities carried out through the internet, leveraging various communication tools like laptops, mobile devices, and computers. Upholding law and order is crucial in thwarting such criminal activities. Cyber attacks stand among the top five global risks. Given the surge in online transactions such as shopping and banking, it's imperative for individuals to grasp self-protection techniques and understand cyber regulations. These regulations empower individuals to act responsibly in the face of potential cyber disasters. This piece delineates prevalent cyber-crimes, the existing cyber laws, and the pressing need to revamp the legal framework governing cyberspace.

KEYWORDS:- Cyber Crime; Cyber Attacks; E-commerce; Cyber Policies, Cyber-stalking, Phishing,

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, our mastery of technology has inadvertently led us to become reliant on it, almost as if we are enslaved by its capabilities. Reflecting on the past, the notion that technology would evolve into an essential requirement for every individual seemed inconceivable [1]. Tasks such as acquiring information at the click of a mouse, engaging in online transactions, and connecting via video calls were once considered daunting prospects. The advent of the internet, however, revolutionized these capabilities, making previously unimaginable feats significantly more accessible and convenient for humankind.

Initially, the internet was utilized for legitimate and specific purposes as people were unaware of its full potential [2-4]. Yet, as its popularity surged, a stark shift occurred in the landscape of internet usage, resulting in a considerable increase in reported cyber-crimes. In 2019, there was a notable spike, with approximately 44,500 reported cyber-crimes. As of 2020, there are around 696.77 million internet users, with 7.5% of them falling victim to cyber-crimes on a quarterly basis [5-9].

Common cyber-crimes encompass phishing, where criminals impersonate trustworthy entities to extract personal information, banking details, or passwords. Online harassment, especially prevalent among teenagers, involves criminals stalking and harassing victims through social media platforms, leading to instances of cyber bullying. Additionally, the invasion of privacy occurs when criminals intrude on an individual's personal life by hacking their computer or monitoring online activities without their consent [10-13].

A myriad of such cyber-crimes exists, prompting the necessity to install and regularly update reliable antivirus

programs. However, the reliability of antivirus software and its ability to guarantee complete protection against cyber-crimes remains questionable.

Hence, specific laws have been established to dissuade potential cyber-criminals, ensuring that individuals contemplate the consequences before engaging in such activities. These laws also dictate the appropriate penalties based on the severity of the crime and the damage inflicted upon the victim [14,15].

II. CLASSIFICATION OF CYBER CRIMES

Cybercrime can be characterized as any criminal act or wrong doing that involves electronic communications, information systems, and devices such as the Internet, or a combination of these elements [16-18].

FIGURE 1: Percentage of Phishing Attacks

Cybercrimes can broadly be classified as follows [19]:

- *Crime against the Individuals*
- *Crimes against Property*
- *Crime against Organization*
- *Crime against Society*

A. CRIME AGAINST THE INDIVIDUALS

Crimes committed against individuals by cybercriminals include:

- **Harassment & Cyberstalking:** Cyberstalking is the act of monitoring an individual's online activities through the internet or electronic means to intimidate, harass, or defame the victim. It often involves various social media platforms, emails, and other digital avenues [23].
- **Cyber Defamation:** Cyber Defamation involves purposefully publishing false and unauthorized information on the internet with the intent to defame, insult, or offend the target [24].
- **Phishing:** Phishing is a cybercrime where the attacker pretends to be a reputable institution to coax individuals into revealing sensitive information like passwords or credit/debit card details, which can then be exploited [25].
- **Spoofing:** Spoofing is a specific cybercrime where the attacker pretends to be a trustworthy source, aiming to access the recipient's personal details or gain control over their system. This form of attack is typically conducted via emails [26].
- **Spamming:** Spamming refers to the distribution of numerous unsolicited messages to a large number of recipients, often for the purpose of commercial advertising [27].

FIGURE 2: Share of Respondents

B. CRIME AGAINST PROPERTY

This cybercrime category involves targeting and causing harm to physical property owned by the victim, like computers or mobile phones. One of the cybercrimes against property is [28-29]:

- **Internet time theft:** This significant global cybercrime occurs when the internet hours purchased or paid for by the victim are utilized by an unauthorized user without the victim's knowledge or awareness of the theft[30].
- **Credit card fraud:** This involves individuals attempting to illicitly obtain a cardholder's payment card details. For instance, they may employ a counterfeit website that appears to be the official site, prompting users to input sensitive information like card numbers, passwords, CVV, etc.
- **Computer Vandalism:** Computer Vandalism is a cybercrime perpetrated through malware (executable programs) capable of causing harm to an entire system or pilfering user data.

FIGURE 3: Data of Property Crime Offense

- **Software piracy:** This refers to the unauthorized creation of duplicate copies of original software and profiting by selling these copies to end-users without legal authorization from the software's owning organization [31].
- **Copyright infringement:** This involves the utilization of copyright-protected content without obtaining permission from the copyright holder. For instance, using copyrighted photos or images for commercial or professional purposes without proper consent [33].
- **Trademark infringement:** This refers to the unauthorized use of a trademark or service mark, violating the policies established by the related Organization .
- **Unauthorized computer access:** Cybercriminals attempt to gain access to an organization's computer system over the internet without authorization. If successful, attackers can potentially harm the system in various ways [40].
- **Unauthorized alteration or deletion of data:** Unauthorized modifications or removal of data without proper authorization.
- **Computer voyeurism:** Involves the unauthorized copying or reading of confidential information by the attacker without making any alterations, leaving the information unchanged.
- **Embezzlement:** Illegally appropriating or misappropriating funds or assets entrusted to an individual, such as an employee, by the organization.

C. CRIME AGAINST ORGANIZATION

Cybercrime targeting a specific organization through the internet to intimidate or threaten it .

- **DOS Attack:** Denial-of-Service attack aims to overwhelm the target's servers by consistently flooding them with fake requests, rendering the service inaccessible for legitimate users. For instance, in 2020, AWS servers were hit by an attack that sent around 2.3 terabits per second of traffic.
- **Email bombing:** A cybercrime wherein the attacker sends a massive volume of emails using botnets to overload the recipient's mailbox, potentially causing server crashes .
- **Data diddling:** Data diddling involves manipulating information either during data entry or by altering the database. This can be carried out through a virus or by a data entry clerk.
- **Salami Attack:** This attack comprises a series of small-scale incursions (salami slicing) that accumulate into a larger attack, often remaining undetected due to its subtle nature. For instance, a criminal might access customers' bank or credit/debit card details from a database and siphon off small amounts from each account, accumulating a significant sum over time.

FIGURE 4: Percentage of Crime Against Organization.

D. CRIME AGAINST SOCIETY

Crime against society refers to crimes that have a widespread impact on the community as a whole.

- **Online gambling:** This refers to a cybercrime conducted over the internet, which may involve activities like sports betting, online casinos, and poker, where currency transactions occur.
- **Forgery:** Forgery involves creating or altering legal documents or instruments, such as producing counterfeit money, stamps, or signatures, often using computers equipped with high-quality devices like printers and scanners.
- **Web jacking:** Similar to hijacking, web jacking involves an attacker gaining control of a website

through illegitimate means. The attacker creates a fake website that appears genuine and places a malicious link on the victim's website. When clicked, this link redirects the victim to the cloned website, resulting in the victim losing complete access to their own website.

- **Cyber trafficking:** This refers to trafficking activities conducted using the internet. It involves the recruitment and advertisement of victims to attract clients. The term "virtual trafficking" can also be used interchangeably with cyber trafficking.

FIGURE 5: Report of Cyber Attack in Society

III. CLASSIFICATION OF CYBER LAWS

- Cyber laws pertain to offenses carried out through the internet, encompassing regulations governing its usage.
- **Manipulating Source Code:** Engaging in the deliberate concealment, alteration, or destruction of a computer's source code when essential may result in imprisonment or a monetary penalty.
- **Unauthorized Use of Passwords:** Misappropriating someone else's password, digital signature, or any unique identification with fraudulent intent could lead to the perpetrator facing imprisonment and fines.
- **Fraudulent Activities with Computer Resources:** If an individual deceives another using computer resources or communication devices, they could face penalties involving imprisonment and fines.
- **Sharing Private Images:** The act of capturing, sharing, or transmitting images of an individual's private areas without their

consent or knowledge is considered a serious offense. Those found guilty may face up to three years of imprisonment or a substantial fine of INR 2 lakhs, or both.

- **Cyber Terrorism Activities:** Any individual attempting to compromise the nation's integrity, sovereignty, or unity by unauthorized access to computer resources or denying access to authorized users could be sentenced to life imprisonment and fined in certain countries.
- **Distribution of Child Pornography:** Those who attempt to capture or distribute inappropriate images involving children under 18 years of age may face imprisonment and fines.
- **Government's Authority to Restrict Websites:** The government holds the power to seize, decrypt, or monitor information transmitted, generated, or stored on computer resources if it is deemed to compromise the nation's integrity and sovereignty. Additionally, the government can block access to certain information.
- **Corporate-Level Data Protection:** If a corporate entity fails to implement necessary security measures that result in unjust loss or gain for any individual, that organization is liable to compensate the affected party.

IV. CLASSIFICATION OF FRAMEWORK TO PREVENT CYBERCRIME RISK.

Cybersecurity framework serves as a universal system and collection of guidelines that allows security leaders in various countries and sectors to comprehend their own security statuses as well as those of their suppliers.[32]

- **NIST Cybersecurity Framework**
- **ISO 27001 and ISO 27002**
- **SOC2**
- **NERC-CIP**
- **HIPAA**
- **GDPR**
- **FISMA**

A. NIST Cybersecurity Framework

The NIST Cybersecurity Framework originated from an executive order issued by former President Obama, titled "Improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity." This order aimed to foster collaboration between the public and private sectors in identifying, assessing, and managing cyber risks. Although compliance with the framework is voluntary, NIST has emerged as the benchmark for evaluating cybersecurity maturity, pinpointing security vulnerabilities, and fulfilling cybersecurity regulations.

FIGURE 6: Journey to NIST to CSF

B. ISO 27001 and ISO 27002

An Internationally recognized standard that outlines the requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining, and continually improving an information security management system (ISMS).

C. SOC2

The Service Organization Control Type 2 is an established cybersecurity framework and auditing standard formulated by the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA). Its primary purpose is to validate that vendors and partners are effectively and securely handling client data. SOC 2 encompasses a comprehensive set of more than 60 compliance requirements and thorough auditing procedures designed for third-party systems and controls. The audit process itself can be lengthy, taking up to a year to complete. Upon completion of the audit, a detailed report is issued, providing an attestation of the vendor's cybersecurity posture. This report serves as an assurance to stakeholders regarding the security measures and practices employed by the vendor in managing sensitive client data.

D. NERC-CIP

The North American Electric Reliability Corporation - Critical Infrastructure Protection (NERC CIP) was introduced as a response to the escalating cyber threats targeting critical infrastructure within the United States. Specifically tailored for the utility and power sector, NERC CIP comprises a set of cybersecurity standards aimed at reducing cyber risk and ensuring the reliability of bulk electric systems.

One of the primary focuses of this framework is to compel organizations within the sector to actively identify and mitigate third-party cyber risks within their supply chains. NERC CIP mandates a range of stringent controls, encompassing various aspects such as categorizing systems and critical assets, providing training for personnel, establishing incident response plans, formulating recovery strategies for critical cyber assets, conducting vulnerability assessments, and more.

Given the complexity and specificity of NERC CIP requirements, organizations within the utility and power sector often seek effective strategies to achieve compliance with these standards. Understanding and implementing these strategies can significantly aid in meeting the stringent cybersecurity measures outlined by NERC CIP, thus fortifying the resilience of critical infrastructure against cyber threats.

E. HIPAA

The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) stands as a cybersecurity framework mandating healthcare organizations to establish controls ensuring the security and confidentiality of electronic health information. HIPAA necessitates compliance measures that encompass various aspects, including employee training and conducting risk assessments to identify and manage emerging cyber risks effectively.

Apart from adhering to standard cybersecurity best practices, such as training employees to handle sensitive health data securely, companies in the healthcare sector are required to conduct thorough risk assessments. These risk assessments are essential for recognizing and managing emerging risks in the evolving landscape of cyber threats.

Despite the significance of HIPAA compliance, healthcare organizations encounter persistent challenges in meeting these requirements, as indicated by research conducted by Bitsight. The complexities and evolving nature of

cybersecurity threats continually challenge healthcare entities in maintaining the stringent standards mandated by HIPAA, highlighting the ongoing difficulties in achieving and maintaining compliance in this sector.

F. GDPR

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) was introduced in 2016 with the aim of reinforcing data protection measures and standards for individuals within the European Union (EU). Its scope encompasses all organizations operating within the EU's jurisdiction and any business that collects and stores private data belonging to EU citizens, thereby extending its impact to include U.S. businesses and other entities outside the EU.

Comprising 99 articles, the GDPR delineates comprehensive compliance responsibilities for companies. These responsibilities cover various aspects, including an individual's rights to access their data, the formulation of robust data protection policies and procedures, stringent requirements for reporting data breaches (mandating companies to inform their national regulatory authority within 72 hours of discovering a breach), and other critical guidelines.

The GDPR imposes substantial penalties for non-compliance. Organizations failing to adhere to its provisions can face severe fines, reaching up to €20,000,000 or 4% of their global annual revenue, whichever is higher. It's noteworthy that the EU authorities are stringent in enforcing these penalties, emphasizing the seriousness with which they approach the protection of individuals' data and the GDPR's enforcement.

G. FISMA

The Federal Information Security Management Act (FISMA) serves as an extensive cybersecurity framework designed to safeguard federal government information and systems from cyber threats. Notably, FISMA's scope extends beyond federal agencies to encompass third-party entities and vendors operating on behalf of these agencies.

Aligned closely with NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) standards, the FISMA framework mandates federal agencies and their third-party associates to uphold certain cybersecurity measures. This includes maintaining a comprehensive inventory of digital assets and identifying any interconnections between networks and systems. Moreover, sensitive information must

be categorized based on risk levels, and security controls must adhere to the minimum security standards outlined in Federal Information Processing Standards (FIPS) and NIST Special Publication 800 series guidelines.

Organizations impacted by FISMA requirements are also obliged to conduct cybersecurity risk assessments, perform annual security reviews, and implement continuous monitoring of their IT infrastructure. These measures aim to ensure a robust defense against cyber threats and uphold the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of government information and systems.

V. INFORMATION ACT 2000

The Information Technology Act of 2000 is a crucial law concerning Indian cyber laws, enacted by the Indian Parliament. This act plays a pivotal role in fostering business through the internet by establishing a framework of rules and regulations governing electronic business transactions. Recognizing the escalating cybercrimes, the Government of India acknowledged the challenges faced by internet users and implemented this act to safeguard their interests. The main objectives and scope of this act are as follows:

1. Objectives:

- The I.T. Act of 2000 aims to grant legal legitimacy to every transaction carried out by using technology or the internet.
- To recognize digital signatures as legally binding for approving any contract online.
- To offer the option to fill out related documents online to enrollment in school or job registration interchange.
- The IT Act of 2000 states that any business can keep their information stored electronically.
- To prevent cybercrime and safeguard the privacy of online users.

2. Scope:

- The IT Act of 2000 covers all electronic information, however it does not cover subsequent electronic transactions.

- The Information Technology Act of 2000 does not apply to the electronic trust-building attestation process. Physical verification is required.
- The Information Technology Act of 2000 does not apply to the attestation of a body's will. It is required that two witnesses physically attest.
- A selling agreement for any type of real estate.
- It is not feasible to certify a property power of attorney using an electronic record.

3. Merits of I.T. Act 2000

- Beneficial for e-commerce promotion
 - Digital signatures,
 - emails
 - credit card payments are all legitimate.
- Online contracts are also legitimate.
- Strengthen the company's operations
- Completing paperwork online
- Strict penalties for online crimes

4. Demerit of I.T. Act 2000

- Copyright infringement is not covered by this statute.
- Domain name protection is nonexistent.
- Wills, trusts, and powers of attorney are not covered by the legislation.
- The Act says nothing about taxes.
- No, the requirement that stamp duty be paid on electronic documents

VI. PREVENTION FOR CYBER CRIMES

It's always preferable to prevent than to cure. Thus, it is imperative that you have strong cyber security to safeguard your important assets, customer information, and operational systems. The protection of networks, systems, and data in cyberspace is known as cyber security. Because cyberspace is uncontrolled, there are many avenues for cybercriminals to target organizations. Therefore, having strong cyber security that safeguards your operating systems, customers' personal information, and important assets is imperative. People, procedure, and technology are the three core areas of good cyber security.

- Exercise caution when sharing photos online, especially with unknown individuals or friends, as they might misuse them.
- Maintain backups of essential information to safeguard against data loss due to virus attacks.
- Refrain from disclosing credit card details on unsecured websites to prevent potential fraud.
- Employ firewalls as they provide added security to your network.
- Avoid sharing personal information online to prevent potential cyber stalking incidents.
- Safeguard your system against viruses by using up-to-date antivirus software.
- Website owners should monitor site traffic for any anomalies or suspicious activities.
- Regularly review system logs and perform audits to identify and trace potential intrusions.
- Clear your browser's cache after completing an online transaction to maintain privacy.
- Respect copyright laws; refrain from using copyrighted material without proper authorization.
- When sharing documents, use ASCII or RTF formats to minimize the risk of transmitting viruses.
- Power down or place computers on standby when not in use.
- Ensure each system or user account has a password for enhanced security.
- Employ advanced security measures like encryption, anonymous browsing, and virtualization software for added protection.

VII. CHALLENGES FACED IN CYBER CRIME

- While good men always have to safeguard everything, bad guys easily break the law.
- Insider scams are more difficult to detect than those committed by outsiders.
- Life is not getting easier with encryption.

- Insufficient personnel or expertise to conduct an investigation or analysis.
- The pace at which the evidence is analyzed.
- Sync corporate policies with various GR compliances and the IT Act.
- Treaties and multi-country jurisdiction are ineffective.
- Most of the time, we believe that we won't become victims of fraud.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Over the past few decades, the Internet has evolved into a sophisticated medium that facilitates the rapid and cost-effective dissemination of information to a global audience of billions. Its unparalleled advantage lies in providing access to a vast worldwide audience without being limited by physical distance or international borders. Internet businesses are often designed to expand sales internationally, transcending geographical boundaries. Consequently, legal disputes arising in cyberspace tend to be complex, with uncertain locations and causes of occurrence. Conflicting laws often stem from ideological disparities, formulated not only by individual countries and their legislatures but also by transnational and sub-national entities.

The outcome is a scenario where the conventional principles of jurisdiction in cybercrime may lead to conflicting jurisdictional claims. There lacks a guiding principle defining the scope of applicability under International or National law. Consequently, the principles become highly personalized and are applied on a case-by-case basis. Nations may rely on various theories such as nationality, universality, protection, and territoriality to justify their exercise of jurisdiction in preventing and investigating certain types of unconventional criminal activities. The crux lies in ensuring that a nation's exercise of jurisdiction, whether to prevent or investigate, is "reasonable" by having a substantial connection with the perpetrator, the crime, or the victim, and aligns logically with adjudication.

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